

Validation of Monte Carlo Code Simulation of 1 MeV Equivalent Neutron Fluence Using a p-i-n Dosimeter Diode in the ENEA Fast Research Reactor RSV TAPIRO

Lorenzo Barcaro^{1,*}, Renato Gatto¹, Alfonso Santagata²

¹Department of Astronautical, Electrical and Energy Engineering, University "La Sapienza", Corso Vittorio Emanuele II, Rome, Italy;

²ENEA - Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development, C.R. Casaccia, Via Anguillarese, S. Maria di Galeria, Italy

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ABSTRACT

The 1-MeV neutron-equivalent fluence is proposed to verify and validate, using experimental data, the Monte Carlo model of the ENEA fast-neutron research reactor RSV TAPIRO. The Monte Carlo simulations, carried out with the combination of MCNP and SERPENT codes, were performed to define the experimental feasibility and conditions. The use of two codes was necessitated by license limitations and the restricted nature of certain reactor-specific information. The 1-MeV neutron equivalent fluences at several positions along radial channel 1 of the TAPIRO reactor were estimated using the SERPENT code within the sensitive volume of the PW34F p-i-n photodiodes. The reactor power, irradiation time, and photodiode positions for the future experimental campaign were defined using simulation results to achieve different neutron fluences. The 1-MeV neutron equivalent fluence measured by the BPW34F photodiodes will be compared with the simulation results reported in this work to validate the use of the available MCNP model of TAPIRO in the design of neutron irradiation experiments for semiconductors

Keywords: Monte Carlo simulation validation, Fast research reactor, Neutron irradiation damage, 1 MeV equivalent neutron fluence, Dosimeter diode

1. INTRODUCTION

The irradiation of semiconductors has been shown to cause important variations in the performance and characteristics of electronic devices. Although this phenomenon has been studied mainly for aerospace applications [1], it also has relevance in other fields: preventing or accounting for such performance variations is essential in scenarios where electronic reliability is critical and intense radiation fields are present. Neutron-induced electronics damage is relevant in nuclear reactors [2], where continuous irradiation can progressively cause drift in some instrumentation. This effect also occurs in particle accelerators, where fast neutrons are primarily produced as secondary radiation from collisions of fast charged particles with targets, and more rarely from undesired interactions with air or structural materials. Fast neutron irradiation causes the displacement of atoms from their reticular positions in a material's crystalline lattice, which leads to the formation of defect clusters in the semiconductor. The defects induced by neutrons in semiconductor-based electronic components can compromise the lifespan of electronic devices in environments such as nuclear facilities, high-energy physics experiments, and aerospace. Therefore, testing electronic components in a neutron field is significant. The durability of electronic components can, in fact, be rapidly tested in nuclear research reactors, where the conditions of real applications are accelerated by high-intensity neutron flux. The ENEA fast research reactor TAPIRO [3, 4] enables this type of test in an almost pure-neutron fission-energy spectrum. Neutron

*barcaro.1963278@studenti.uniroma1.it

irradiation of electronic components was performed several times in the TAPIRO reactor [3, 5], and the neutron damage was always evaluated using the 1-MeV equivalent fluence on silicon, as illustrated in the following paragraph. The determination of the 1-MeV equivalent fluence at the end of an irradiation is assessed by multiplying the measured neutron fluence by the hardness parameter calculated using the neutron damage function [6] and the neutron spectrum estimated by the MCNP code [7] with the TAPIRO model described in [8]. In future neutron irradiations of semiconductors, it is intended to use a different methodology based on a p-i-n photodiode as a neutron dosimeter. In fact, in some p-i-n photodiodes, prolonged exposure to such environments was shown to result in a variation in device gain, making these diodes effective dose-monitoring instruments [9]. To define the new procedure, preliminary measurements are planned before the end of 2025 using the p-i-n BPW34F photodiode at different positions along radial channel 1 of the TAPIRO reactor. The experimental findings from the preliminary measurements will also be used to validate the MCNP model of the TAPIRO reactor for the design of neutron-irradiation experiments for semiconductors.

Due to their availability, low cost, and sensitivity to displacement damage, BPW34F photodiodes (produced by OSRAM [10]) have been extensively characterized at the CERN IRRAD1 and IRRAD2 facilities and have been used there for neutron fluence measurements. By irradiating such diodes with fast neutron sources and measuring the devices' gain after irradiation, a calibration curve relating voltage to equivalent fluence was obtained, providing a practical way to measure equivalent fluence at a position of interest. These diodes can be used simultaneously or in substitution to other validation strategies as a means to validate neutron transport simulations without the need for expensive equipment: by measuring the device's gain after irradiation and referring to the calibration curve, an equivalent fluence can be experimentally determined and compared with the computed value. In this work, the first part of the procedure has been executed with a SERPENT2 [11] Monte Carlo simulation. External source mode was selected, given that its validation in SERPENT2 has received less attention than the criticality calculation mode. The requirement for a neutron source that is both reliably characterized and that offers an environment suitable for neutron damage experimental campaigns was satisfied by the RSV TAPIRO reactor: an extensively validated MCNP simulation was used to determine the neutron energy spectrum across several positions in one of the irradiation channels (Radial Channel 1), and these spectra were then utilized in SERPENT2 to run simulations using a model of the BPW34F diodes. MCNP also estimated the 1-MeV equivalent fluences as an average over a void sphere of 1 cm in diameter, centered at the considered radial channel 1 positions. This allowed a comparison between MCNP and SERPENT2 results, providing information on whether such a detailed model is necessary for accurate equivalent fluence calculation. In the preliminary experimental campaign, measuring the forward voltage of the BPW34F diodes at 1 mA of current with a 700 ms pulse width at different neutron fluences will allow the construction of a voltage-versus-equivalent-fluence calibration curve to compare with those already available in the literature. The simulation data are sufficient to plan the preliminary experimental campaign, whose characteristics are also described in the following.

This work was undertaken as part of a collaborative agreement between ENEA and Sapienza University of Rome. The MCNP simulations were performed using a single-user license available at ENEA, whereas the SERPENT simulations were carried out at the University. The use of two different Monte Carlo codes was dictated by practical constraints, including license availability and the restricted nature of some reactor-specific information. If these limitations were not present, performing both the criticality calculation and the diode-response simulation within a single code would have been preferable.

2. DEFINITION OF MEANINGFUL QUANTITIES

To effectively evaluate neutron-induced damage, in semiconductor irradiation studies, it is common to use energy-dependent damage functions [6], which are usually expressed as the ratio of a measurable damage metric to the neutron fluence responsible for producing that effect. A widely adopted damage indicator based on this principle is the gain variation in bipolar junction transistors under irra-

diation, which has been shown to correlate with the microscopic displacement kerma factor (hereafter indicated as $F_{D,Si}(E)$), representing the kinetic energy per unit target atom and per unit neutron fluence responsible for lattice atoms' displacement. It can be derived from cross sections, a partition function that distinguishes the portion of kerma that contributes to displacement rather than ionization, and kinematic relations derived from conservation laws. Its energy dependence is tabulated pointwise in [6]. These tabulated values can be directly employed to construct the displacement damage response function used as a tally weighting function in Monte Carlo codes.

The definition of $F_{D,Si}(E)$ allows the introduction of the equivalent neutron fluence for a given material at a reference energy (conventionally chosen as 1 MeV in silicon). This parameter enables quantification of the severity of the radiation environment without requiring considerations of the spectrum shape or the energy dependence of radiation effects. The definition is a statement of equivalence in damage:

$$\Phi_{1\text{MeVeq,Si}} = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} F_{D,Si}(E)\Phi(E)dE}{F_{D,Si,1\text{MeV}}} \quad (1)$$

Here $F_{D,Si,1\text{MeV}}$ denotes the value assumed by the function $F_{D,Si}(E)$ at $E = 1$ MeV. An additional spectrum descriptor is the hardness parameter. Being independent of the total neutron fluence, it is a valuable metric for comparing radiation environments exclusively based on different spectral shapes and independently of the source's intensity:

$$H = \frac{\Phi_{1\text{MeVeq,Si}}}{\Phi} = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} F_{D,Si}(E)\Phi(E)dE}{F_{D,Si,1\text{MeV}} \int_0^{\infty} \Phi(E)dE} \quad (2)$$

The damage function presented is considered reliable when displacement damage is mainly caused by non-monochromatic spectra with energies above 100 keV, as monochromatic spectra can introduce considerable uncertainty due to resonance peaks.

3. RSV TAPIRO RESEARCH REACTOR

As suggested by its name (Reattore Sorgente Veloce TARatura Pila Rapita potenza 0) the RSV TAPIRO is a zero power fast research reactor located at ENEA Casaccia Research Center (near Rome, Italy) [3, 4]. Inspired by the Argonne Fast Source Reactor, since reaching its first criticality in 1971 it has been used for several activities, including the irradiation of electromechanical devices, testing of measurement chains, validation of codes and simulations and neutron activation analysis. RSV TAPIRO is a helium cooled reactor, provided with a cylindrical core made of highly enriched U-Mo, measuring 120 mm in diameter and with a height-to-diameter ratio close to 1. The core consists of an upper fixed section and a lower movable part, both contained in a thin steel casing. A copper radial reflector surrounds the core, extending up to a radius of 40 cm. Its biological shielding is constructed from high density borated concrete in a nearly spherical shape. Multiple irradiation channels are available: three of them are located at the reactor midplane, one is tangential to the top edge of the core, and a thermal column is also present, where neutron moderators can be inserted to obtain softer spectra. Consequently, the reactor can be used to perform experiments that may require a wide variety of neutron spectra, including an almost pure U-235 fission spectrum within the core, accessible via the diametral channel. The diametral channel, with a diameter of 1 cm, crosses the fixed upper section of the core, where a flux of $4 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ can be reached at the maximum power of 5 kW. The tangential channel is oriented parallel to the diametral one, while the remaining two midplane channels penetrate radially into the reflector. The primary one, Radial Channel 1, is oriented orthogonally to the axis of the diametral channel, its nearest end is located 9.3 cm from the core and has a gradually reducing cross section to reduce neutron streaming. The reactor is equipped with two safety rods, two shim rods, and one regulation

rod, all made of copper. When inserted into cavities located inside the reflector, due to copper's reflective properties, a positive reactivity insertion occurs. In addition, the reactor has a redundant safety mechanism, referred to as a "safety plug", responsible for the motion of the lower section of the core and required to achieve criticality. If a fast shutdown was required, the safety plug would immediately separate the lower core portion from the upper one.

As demonstrated by previous experimental campaigns, RSV TAPIRO reactor is a valid neutron source for conducting the irradiation of silicon based devices [4]. The conditions achievable in Radial Channel 1 were considered appropriate for conducting the experiment: unlike the diametral channel, its dimensions allow for the insertion of irradiation devices while maintaining a sufficiently hard spectrum and a relatively short distance from the core, obtaining sufficiently high equivalent fluence levels, which are crucial given the constraints on irradiation time and reactor power.

4. SIMULATION: MODEL AND RESULTS

In the experimental configuration, eleven diodes will be installed at 5 cm intervals, covering positions from 10 cm to 60 cm from the core inside Radial Channel 1, with sufficient spacing to limit mutual interference, as shown in Figure 1. The same detector arrangement was reproduced in the MCNP model to ensure consistency between simulation and experimental conditions. Neutron flux spectra were estimated using MCNP as the average within a 0.5 cm-radius sphere centered at each diode location. These spectra were used as source terms for 11 separate SERPENT2 simulations, each using the same diode geometry but a unique flux input.

Figure 1. View of the RSV TAPIRO layout and diode positioning in the MCNP model: (Left) horizontal view of the reactor layout with irradiation channels highlighted (from [12], modified); (Right) placement of the diodes in the 11 MCNP positions of radial channel 1, where the spheres correspond to cells 5000-5010 in the MCNP model (diodes 1-11), visualized using the MCNP plotter.

Although MCNP could have tallied all positions in a single run, SERPENT2 required separate simulations. To improve accuracy at greater distances from the core, a second MCNP run with more particle histories was conducted to have the same uncertainty level in each sphere. Due to limited data on material composition and dimensional tolerances in the diode datasheet, several uncertainties remain. For modeling purposes, copper was assumed for the pins, silicon for the chip, and BADGE-type epoxy resin for the plastic support. Although more detailed specifications were unavailable, their omission is unlikely to significantly affect the results, given the diode's small size and low-density material.

To simulate each diode, 10^{10} neutron histories were generated isotropically within a thin spherical shell (radii 0.499-0.500 cm). The copper reflector surrounding the irradiation positions produces significant

backscattering, making the isotropic approximation acceptable, though not exact. A more accurate evaluation will be performed in future using a single-code SERPENT simulation. As shown in Figure 2, flux profiles exhibit an approximately exponential decrease with distance from the reactor core.

Figure 2. Comparison of neutron flux profiles in silicon obtained from MCNP and SERPENT2 simulations. The vertical axis is shown in logarithmic scale for improved visibility. The plot includes the MCNP source flux, the SERPENT2 neutron flux in silicon, and the resulting 1 MeV equivalent flux in silicon (Si 1 MeV_{eq} Flux). The position-dependent energy spectrum is also shown in four canonical energy groups: thermal (0-0.5 eV), epithermal (0.5 eV-10 keV), intermediate (10 keV-1 MeV), and fast (1-20 MeV).

To estimate the impact of MCNP uncertainties on SERPENT2 outputs, a simplified method was used, as more rigorous methods, such as the Total Monte Carlo approach [13], were computationally time-consuming. Assuming the average silicon flux scales with external source intensity, the relative uncertainty of the source was combined in quadrature with the statistical uncertainty of the SERPENT2 output. However, this method captures only the overall source-intensity uncertainty and neglects the uncertainty in each spectrum's bin. Consequently, the SERPENT2 flux results and the hardness parameter reflect only simulation statistical uncertainty, despite being influenced by spectral shape. This limitation is particularly relevant for the 1 MeV neutron equivalent flux: spectral bin uncertainties should be weighted by the damage function to compute total uncertainty, but only source intensity uncertainty was considered in this case. The difference between the 1 MeV equivalent flux and the SERPENT2 average flux arises from the spectrum's shape. In general terms, above 100 keV neutron-induced damage tends to increase with energy (though this is a simplified view, as the damage function includes resonances and follows a complex trend). Consequently, when the average neutron energy is significantly lower than 1 MeV, the resulting 1 MeV equivalent flux is lower than the total neutron flux, reflecting the reduced contribution of lower energy neutrons to displacement damage.

As expected, the discrepancy between the MCNP source flux and the SERPENT2 flux is minimal, since attenuation in the diode materials is negligible due to their limited dimensions and low densities. The SERPENT2 flux is slightly higher than the MCNP value, but the two remain consistent within the tolerances relevant for experimental design. This increase is likely due to the absence of a straightforward method for defining a spherical surface source in SERPENT2: the source was instead implemented within a small volume, causing some neutrons to originate closer to the silicon chip than the intended

0.5 cm radius, hence increasing their interaction probability and the resulting flux. A further contribution may arise from the omission of air in the SERPENT2 model between the diode and the spherical boundary. In Figure 2, the neutron spectrum is also presented across radial channel 1, divided into four canonical energy groups: thermal (0-0.5 eV), epithermal (0.5 eV-10 keV), intermediate (10 keV-1 MeV), and fast (1-20 MeV). Due to the RSV TAPIRO being a fast reactor, the thermal and epithermal components are essentially negligible, while the intermediate and fast groups prevail. The epithermal group shows an initial concavity opposite that of the intermediate and fast groups, suggesting that a portion of neutrons thermalized in the first two groups accumulates here, slowing the rate of epithermal flux reduction with distance. The thermal group remains negligible, though its relative error visibly decreases with distance, likely due to increased thermalization and consequent improved statistics.

In Figure 3, the hardness parameter data are shown. As the distance from the core increases, neutrons undergo thermalization, resulting in a decrease in average energy up to 45 cm, corresponding to the first position outside the external radius of the copper reflector.

Figure 3. Hardness parameter profiles in silicon: (Left) MCNP vs SERPENT2 comparison; (Right) SERPENT2 to MCNP ratio.

Thermalization leads to a narrowing of the energy range where both the damage function and the neutron spectrum are significant, causing the observed reduction in equivalent flux. At around 45 cm, the hardness parameter reaches a minimum. Both the neutron flux and the 1-MeV equivalent flux decrease as the distance from the core increases. Outside the copper reflector, however, the neutron flux decreases more rapidly than the 1-MeV equivalent flux, making the ratio of equation (2) grow and then the hardness parameter. The concrete of the biological shielding increases the epithermal and thermal neutrons, reducing the fast neutrons, but the 1-MeV equivalent flux reduction is slower than the increase in the total flux. Figure 3 also compares hardness parameters obtained from MCNP and SERPENT2 simulations. While the values are generally close, SERPENT2 consistently returns slightly and systematically lower values. This is likely due to neutron interactions with the silicon diode modeled in SERPENT2, which can slightly reduce neutron energy, although the impact is minimal due to the diode's small size and low density. The main results of this section are presented in Table I.

Table I. Unified comparison of fluxes and hardness parameters between SERPENT2 and MCNP across positions, including relative statistical uncertainties. All fluxes are normalized per unit power.

Pos. (cm)	SERPENT2			MCNP		
	Φ ($\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}\text{W}^{-1}$)	$\Phi_{1\text{MeV}_{\text{eq,Si}}}$ ($\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}\text{W}^{-1}$)	H	Φ ($\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}\text{W}^{-1}$)	$\Phi_{1\text{MeV}_{\text{eq,Si}}}$ ($\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}\text{W}^{-1}$)	H
10.0	1.80e+09 0.2%	1.05e+09 0.2%	0.58 0.1%	1.65e+09 0.1%	9.61e+08 0.2%	0.58 0.1%
15.0	1.17e+09 0.2%	5.87e+08 0.2%	0.50 0.2%	1.07e+09 0.2%	5.38e+08 0.2%	0.50 0.2%
20.0	7.73e+08 0.2%	3.36e+08 0.2%	0.44 0.2%	7.05e+08 0.2%	3.07e+08 0.2%	0.44 0.2%
25.0	5.09e+08 0.3%	1.97e+08 0.3%	0.39 0.3%	4.64e+08 0.2%	1.81e+08 0.3%	0.39 0.3%
30.0	3.33e+08 0.3%	1.16e+08 0.3%	0.35 0.3%	3.02e+08 0.3%	1.06e+08 0.3%	0.35 0.3%
35.0	2.10e+08 0.4%	6.88e+07 0.4%	0.33 0.4%	1.92e+08 0.4%	6.29e+07 0.4%	0.33 0.4%
40.0	1.25e+08 0.5%	3.77e+07 0.5%	0.30 0.5%	1.14e+08 0.5%	3.45e+07 0.5%	0.30 0.5%
45.0	6.97e+07 0.2%	1.99e+07 0.2%	0.29 0.2%	6.36e+07 0.2%	1.83e+07 0.2%	0.29 0.2%
50.0	3.93e+07 0.3%	1.17e+07 0.3%	0.30 0.3%	3.58e+07 0.2%	1.07e+07 0.3%	0.30 0.3%
55.0	2.50e+07 0.3%	7.95e+06 0.4%	0.32 0.4%	2.28e+07 0.3%	7.26e+06 0.4%	0.32 0.4%
60.0	1.88e+07 0.4%	6.31e+06 0.4%	0.34 0.4%	1.71e+07 0.4%	5.79e+06 0.4%	0.34 0.4%

The apparent similarity between the spatial trends of the total flux and the 1 MeV equivalent flux does not imply that the neutron spectrum remains unchanged along the channel. A quantitative comparison, as reported in Table I, shows that the relative differences between the two fluxes vary with position. A closer inspection of the curves in Figures 2 and 3 reveals that, in the region closest to the core, the equivalent flux decreases more rapidly than the total flux. This is consistent with the reduction of the hardness parameter and indicates a significant spectral softening, driven by the progressive loss of the fast and intermediate neutron component that dominates the damage response in silicon. Further from the core, the situation becomes more complex, as both flux curves exhibit a change in concavity around 40-45 cm, coinciding with the minimum of the hardness parameter. In this region, the difference between total and equivalent flux reaches its maximum. Beyond this point, the equivalent flux decreases more slowly, which is plausibly due to the fact that the spectrum is increasingly dominated by neutrons below roughly 100 keV, which contribute only marginally to the 1 MeV equivalent fluence. The graphical similarity of the two flux profiles is only apparent, as the hardness parameter and the numerical ratio between total and equivalent flux clearly demonstrate position-dependent spectral variations.

5. CONCLUSIONS

An experimental procedure was proposed to validate Monte Carlo simulations and codes, by monitoring $\Phi_{1\text{MeV}_{\text{eq,Si}}}$ via voltage readout using OSRAM BPW34F p-i-n diodes. In presenting the methodology, RSV TAPIRO was confirmed as an appropriate source. SERPENT2 simulations revealed a predictable exponential decrease in fluence with increasing distance from the core. The hardness parameter showed a non-monotonic trend with a minimum near the reflector radius, due to a faster decrease in equivalent fluence compared to neutron fluence. The information obtained from the study is sufficient to define irradiation plans once the facility-specific constraints (such as maximum available power and irradiation time) are established. These plans can then be tailored to reproduce the calibration curve reported in [9], or, alternatively, to use that curve to convert the measured voltage variation into an equivalent 1 MeV neutron fluence, thereby enabling the determination of the neutron fluence from the measured equivalent fluence and the simulated hardness parameter. Future work will involve performing the irradiation campaign and comparing the measurements with the simulated predictions, providing valuable validation of both the calibration curves available in the literature and the adopted Monte Carlo models.

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